

Passive Copy-Move Image Forgery Detection Techniques: A Study

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Abstract—Due to the tremendous technological development in the digital world, there is a proliferation in the popularity of digital images in all spheres of human life. However, the introduction of state of the art Digital Image-Editing Software packages such as Pic Monkey, Adobe Lightroom, Corel PaintShop, Skylum Luminar, etc. have made image forgery non-observable and much easier than earlier times. Thus, there is a need for image authentication and forgery detection. This paper presents the active and passive image forgery detection techniques in use and then draws a comparative study of several existing passive frequency-based copy-move forgery detection approaches depending on evaluation metrics such as precision, recall and F-Measure. This paper also discusses the various forgery detection datasets with their features, advantages, and disadvantages along with the different practical evaluation metrics used by researchers for assessing the performance of the image forgery detection algorithms.

Keywords— *Digital Image Forensics, Image Authentication, Passive Copy-Move Forgery, Geometric Transformation, DCT*

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently, digital images are considered as one of the most prominently used information distribution medium because they can strongly influence the viewers by storing pictorial memory and evidence. But at the same time, these images can be used as a misleading tool for hiding facts and evidences by creating the forged version of the same images. The concept of image forgery is not new to the humans. In the past, the process of image forgery was very much challenging and time consuming because of the availability of limited image editing software packages at that time. However, with the advancement of image editing software tools and devices, it became very easy to alter the image to such a perfection that

forgery cannot be perceived by the human naked eye. As a result, there is a dearth of trust over digital image authenticity. This forced researchers to develop different techniques for detecting the forgeries or modifications in order to validate the integrity of digital images. Thus, image forgery detection (IFD) has grabbed the

The remaining paper is organized into succeeding sections: Section II discusses the Digital Image Forgery detection approaches. Copy-move forgery detection techniques based on their individual classifications are assembled in Section III. The Key Challenges in copy-move forgery detection are discussed in Section IV. The conclusion derived from this study paper is presented in Section V.

II. DIGITAL IMAGE FORGERY DETECTION APPROACHES

In the literature, IFD approaches are extensively classified into Active or Non-Blind [1] and Passive or Blind techniques [2] as shown in Figure 1. The former techniques are additionally classified into Digital Watermarking and Digital Signature. The digital watermarking is further sub-divided into fragile, semi-fragile, and robust while digital Signature is sub-divided into a generic signature, robust signature, and distributed source coding. These techniques have solved the image authenticity problem to a more considerable extent, but the main drawback is that they require prior information about the image and superior hardware or software (high-cost) to insert the watermark into the image before it is transmitted to the receiver. Also, the continuous processing of the image degrades its original visual quality which limits its use in practice. While as in the latter case a digital investigator does not necessarily require any preceding information about the image but utilizes only the statistics and content of the image to detect the forgery. Thus, passive approaches are frequently adopted for forgery detection in comparison to active approaches. Passive techniques are commonly categorized into five types: Pixel based, Camera-based, Physics-based, Format based and Geometry based techniques [3]. The brief description of each of the above-mentioned image forgery detection techniques is given below.

A. Format-Based Techniques

This type of forgery detection technique is based on the image format and the most common image formats used today is the lossy JPEG compression. In JPEG compression, the image is first represented as a Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) blocks. The resulting coefficients from DCT are then quantized in order to achieve compression. The blocking and the quantization process introduces certain artifacts in the image, which are later used to identify the forgery. These detection techniques are divided into three types viz; Double compression, JPEG Blocking, and JPEG Quantization and are shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Categorization of digital image forgery detection techniques

B. Camera-Based Techniques

Nowadays, most of the images are acquired by using different high resolution and low-cost digital cameras such as Canon, Nikon, Sony, Olympus, etc. rather than typical film cameras. Since these cameras are not perfect imaging systems because various artifacts are present regarding each step of the imaging process in them. The artifacts can be used to associate an image with a specific camera and hence makes the forgery detection possible.

C. Physics-Based Techniques

When two or more than two images which are captured in different conditions, i.e., different lighting or brightness it becomes almost impossible for the forgers to match the unlike conditions of the separate images. Such physics based features of the images can be utilized for detecting digital image forgery.

D. Geometry-Based Techniques

When the unforged image is manipulated by using different processes such as shifting of an object or region in the image, translation or combining the existing image with another image then the position of the principal point (i.e. the point where a principal plane intersects the axis) changes which otherwise, always lies close to the centre of the image. The geometric based techniques utilize different available image features such as dimension, position of objects related to the camera, etc. to detect the forgery.

E. Pixel-Based Techniques

Pixel-based image forgery detection techniques identify the image forgery either directly or indirectly by accentuating on the pixel related characteristics or statistical changes of the suspected image. These techniques are broadly categorized into three types: Photomontage or Image Splicing, Image Resampling, and Copy-move forgery (CMF) or Image Cloning. In the first type, the regions from two or more different images are combined to form a significantly different image from the original. Image splicing is further divided into two types: Region based and Boundary based [4]. Image resampling involves scaling, rotating, skewing, flipping or stretching the portions of the image in order to create a realistic match or high quality forged image. While resampling an image, specific periodic correlations are introduced in its samples which can be later used to detect the image forgery. This type of forgery is less harmful as compared to the others. In the third type of forgery, copied portion belongs to the same image. Among these three types of forgeries, copy-move forgery is the most common and popular because it requires only one image. Copy-move forgery and Image splicing are usually accompanied by different types of post-processing operations such as adding noise, JPEG compression, and image blurring or geometrical operations such as rotation, scaling and shifting, thereby, making the forgery detection difficult. The portion of the image manipulated by copy-move forgery by using different sophisticated image editing tools such as Skylum Luminar, Photoshop etc. is unnoticeable to the human naked eye. Thus, detecting signs of such forgery is a critical problem in image forensics. However, the key issue with aforesaid forgery detection is the computational complexity.

From the broad categorization of digital image forgery detection techniques shown in Figure 1, it is concluded that the IFD technique is multidimensional and various characteristics and features can be used for it. It is also concluded that the Pixel based IFD techniques are the most effective as compared to others because these techniques neither require any previous knowledge about the transformation performed over image region nor require any information regarding how image acquisition has been made.

III. COPY-MOVE FORGERY DETECTION

In general, copy-move forgery detection techniques are divided into two types namely; Key-point based [5] and Block based methods [6] and are depicted in Figure 1. Key-point centered methods don't sub-divide the image into blocks. These techniques are based on identifying and selecting the high entropy image regions. The features are then extracted corresponding to each key-point and later matched to find the copied portion. The popular key-point based methods include Scale Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) [7], Speeded-up Robust Features (SURF) [8] and Position Relationship of Key-points [9]. The key-point based forgery detection methods cannot adequately distinguish the CMF when the copy and pasted portion is an even part, because key-points cannot be extracted from those parts and hence these methods are not much accurate in comparison to their counterpart block-based ones. Further, the performance of these methods degrades on applying different common image processing operations such as scaling, rotation, etc. which limits the use of these methods for detecting post-processed copied regions.

On the contrary side, block-based methods sub-divide the image into non-overlapping/overlapping blocks of well-defined size rather than examining the whole image at same time as shown in the block diagram in Figure 2. After blocking the image, these methods extract a feature vector from each block. Different feature vector extraction algorithms are used in different image forgery detection techniques. The extracted features are subsequently matched in order to detect the forged portion. However, before block tiling, the pre-processing operations such as noise removal, color to grayscale conversion are applied to the input image. Finally, the post-processing step is used to check the accuracy of the CMFD technique against different operations such as compression, scaling, etc. Block-based methods are further divided into frequency, intensity, dimensionality reduction, and moment-based CMFD techniques as shown in Figure 1. However, in this paper, only frequency based CMFD techniques are discussed.

Fig. 2. A general block diagram of Block-Based CMFD [10]

The primary effort at detecting CMF was described in [11]. Subsequently, a considerable amount of research has been carried out in the field of CMFD. Some of the recent and relevant frequency based IFD techniques by various researchers is as follows.

Mohammed Hazim Alkawaz et al. [12] implemented the block-based CMFD method using DCT coefficients. In order to investigate the effects of different block size ranging from 4 x 4 and 8 x 8 pixels on the performance of the False Positive(FP) and False Negative(FN), threshold $D_{\text{similar}} = 0.1$ and distance threshold $(N)_d = 100$ are used to implement the ten input images. Consequently, 8x8 overlapping blocks outperformed as compared to the 4x4 overlapping blocks in terms of precision, recall,

and F-measure. Also, the accuracy performance of different block sizes varies with the threshold value, forged region area and distance between the two forged regions.

Li. Yuenan [13] examined the CMFD algorithm based on polar cosine transform (PCT) and approximate nearest neighbor searching. The rotationally-invariant and orthogonal properties of the PCT are used to extract the robust and compact features from overlapping patches. The possible similar regions are detected by identifying the patches with similar features which is expressed as approximate nearest neighbor searching and solved by employing Locality-Sensitive Hashing (LSH). Also LSH based alikepatch detection approach is enough effective than the popular lexicographical sorting. The accuracy of the proposed scheme is further enhanced by developing a set of post-verification criteria in order to filter out the false matches. The experimental results revealed that this method can withstand against various post-processing operations such as rotation etc.

The authors [14] proposed CMFD technique based on the hybrid transform i.e. DCT and DWT. The suspicious input image is first divided into blocks using a discrete wavelet transform, and the DCT is applied to those blocks. The correlation coefficients then compare the individual blocks. The authors also developed unique multiplication mask based IFD method in order to test the efficacy of the method. The presented image forgery detection method can detect both copy-move and Image splicing types of forgeries.

Toqeer Mahmood et al. [15] suggested an efficient and effective technique for the detection of region duplication forgery in digital images. The region duplication forgery detection (RDFD) is achieved by using the Stationary Wavelet Transform (SWT) based features. Toqeer Mahmood et al.'s technique divides the approximation sub-band of SWT into overlapping block sizes such as 4x4 and 8x8. The experimental results showed that 4x4 overlapping blocks produce more false detection thereby affecting the performance of the RDFD algorithm. The proposed technique makes use of reduced length of the feature vector which helps in reducing the execution time of the algorithm.

The comparison of some of the recent frequency-based CMFD methods such as DCT, PCT, DWT, hybrid (DCT+DWT) transform, stationary wavelet transform, local binary pattern, Fourier Mellin, transform and polar complex exponential transform based on practical performance evaluation metrics, i.e., precision, recall, and F-measure is presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1. COMPARISON OF FREQUENCY-BASED IFD METHODS IN TERMS OF PRECISION, RECALL AND F-MEASURE

Author	Method	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	Measure
MH Alkawaz et al. [12]	Discrete Cosine Transform(D	64.5 29	96.5 79	75.16 6

	CT)			
Li. Yuenan [13]	Polar Cosine Transform (PCT)	98	99	98
K. Hayat et al. [14]	DWT+DCT	72.5 0	96.3 0	81.80 1
Toqeer Mahmood et al. [15]	Stationary Wavelet Transform (SWT)	98.8 35	95.5 18	97.02 8
Reza Davarzani et al. [16]	Local Binary Pattern (LBP)	93.5 7	90.4 5	91.98
M. Bashir et al. [17]	Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT)	95.5 5	72.4 5	88.86
S. Bayram et al. [18]	Fourier Mellin Transform (FMT)	96.3 8	17.8 7	30.15
M. Emam et al. [19]	Polar Complex Exponential Transform (PCET)	88.5	76.9	82.3

From Table 1, it is clear that Li. Yuenan's [13] Locality-Sensitive Hashing (LSH) based similar patch identification, and post verification method produces accurate forgery detection results as compared to the other mentioned methods. In DCT [12] and SWT [15] forgery detection methods, 8x8 overlapping blocks performed better than 4x4 overlapping blocks in terms of precision and recall. Further, in both of these methods, the accuracy performance of different overlapping blocks is influenced by the size of the copied area, the distance between the two replicated regions and the threshold value employed in the IFD algorithm. Toqeer Mahmood et al. [15] improved the forgery detection time of the algorithm by using the reduced length of the feature vector. While as S. Bayram et al. [18] achieved the improved executive time at the expense of a slight reduction in the robustness of the algorithm.

The main advantage of K. Hayat et al.[14] method, as compared to the other methods mentioned in Table 1 is that it is viable for both Copy-move and image splicing forgery detection. However, the performance of the method can reduce in the presence of occlusion. Further, the methods proposed in [13],[16],[18],[19] are robust to various geometrical post-processing operations such as Lossy JPEG compression, rotation, scaling, blurring and additive white Gaussian noise, etc. However, M. Bashar et al. [17] method (95.55% precision and 72.45% recall) performs well in the artifact-free environment. Although Reza Davarzani et al. [16] method is robust to various geometrical operations, it is still time-consuming for IFD in high-resolution images.

IV. KEY CHALLENGES IN CMF DETECTION

Despite the speedy development and huge techniques that have been recommended to tackle the problem of CMF, those techniques however, have some disadvantages and challenges [20]. Among these challenges, the benchmark dataset and the evaluation metrics are crucial. Datasets are considered as an integral part of current computer vision investigation. Copy-move forgery detection is one of the hot research topics of computer vision investigation and has its dedicated datasets. In this section, the datasets, with their features, advantages, and disadvantages are discussed in subsection A, and the evaluation metrics are presented in sub-section B.

A. Benchmark Datasets for CMFD

There are seven datasets, i.e., MICC, Image Manipulation Dataset, CoMoFoD, CMFddb_grip, Copy-Move Hard (CMH), Copy-Move Forgery (CMF) Dataset, and COVERAGE [21] which are freely accessible and have been used by researchers for evaluating and comparing the performance of different competitive algorithms.

- **MICC:** MICC is one of the oldest datasets that are available online. It consists of four subsets, i.e., MICC-F220, MICC-F2000, MICC-F8multi and MICC-F600. In the first two subsets of this dataset, the size of the square or rectangular copied area is 1.2% and 1.12% of the whole image respectively. In the third and fourth subsets, it varies. The first limitation of this dataset is that the forged images are produced by using only two types of attacks, i.e., rotation and scaling. Also, the forged images created by MICC have no post-processing operation such as JPEG compression. Second, the first three subsets have no ground truth images which makes the performance evaluation of IFD algorithm inaccurate. However, this dataset has an advantage of restrained attack levels, which permits in-depth analysis of the correlation between the detection accuracy of the algorithm and the different levels of an attack.

- **Image Manipulation Dataset:** Image Manipulation Dataset, a ground truth database, was built by using high resolution images from consumer cameras. It consists a total of 48 base images. This dataset allows the in-depth analysis of the robustness of realistic copy-move forgery detection algorithm against rotation with a range of angles. The performance analysis of the block based algorithms using this dataset is time-consuming because of the large size of the images, mainly if the algorithm is implemented using MATLAB. Additionally, the time and the effort needed to evaluate the performance

of an algorithm may double in regards to comparing the results with another algorithm that has not been evaluated previously using this dataset. Another disadvantage is the lack of some of the attacks, such as blur, and the lack of other possible combinations of attacks, such as rotate-scale-noise.

- **CoMoFoD:** Tralic et al. proposed the CoMoFoD dataset. This dataset consists of small-sized and large-sized images dataset. Each dataset contains the original images with more types of frequent attacks, i.e., distortion, and post-processing attacks, such as color reduction as compared to the Image manipulation dataset and MICC, which makes the total number of images to be 3000 and 10,000, respectively. The main advantage of this dataset is the broad range of attacks with different levels which allows the in-depth study of different forgery detection techniques. However, the large number of images in the CoMoFoD dataset limits its use in practice. Additionally, the size of the forged portion varies from large to significantly small, which makes setting the threshold very difficult.

- **CMFDDb_grip:** Cozzolino et al. presented CMFDDb_grip dataset. They used this dataset for the performance evaluation of their copy-move forgery detection algorithm. This dataset has low variance in the sizes of the copy-move forged areas. Also, the images of this dataset can be considered of average size as compared to the other six datasets. However, the main disadvantage of this dataset is the absence of some common attacks such as Image Blurring or the combinations of attacks. Another disadvantage is that this dataset is not completely downloadable but can be created using the available code. However, if any change occurs in the values of the different parameters of the code than some alterations get introduced in the generated dataset which in turn limits the comparability of the results with other researchers who used the same dataset.

- **Copy-Move Hard (CMH):** Tiago Carvalho et al. developed CMH dataset. It consists of 108 PNG format realistic duplicate images. The resolution of the images of this dataset varies from 845x634 pixels (the smallest) to 1296x972 pixels (the biggest) and also each image has its ground truth available. Although the parameters, scaling factor and angle of rotation used in this dataset is broad, but the total number of images is minimal which may not be enough to evaluate the performance of CMF algorithm precisely. In addition, CMH dataset shares numerous shortcomings with other datasets discussed earlier, the considerable difference of the size of the forged area, the lack of post-processing attacks, the size of the images and the irregular levels of rotation and scaling attacks.

- **Copy-Move Forgery Dataset:** This dataset of 1020 images was created by Edoardo Ardizzone et al. to evaluate the performance of their CMFD system. This dataset consists of medium sized images (almost all 1000×700 or 700×1000 pixels), and it is sub-divided into four subsets D0, D1, D2, and D3. In the first subset of 50 images, the cloned area merely is copied and then pasted at some other place within the same image. The D1 subset comprises of 600 tampered images in which each copy-move area is rotated according to the ranges of $[25^\circ, 25^\circ]$, $[0^\circ, 360^\circ]$, $[-5^\circ, 5^\circ]$ with steps of 5° , 30° , 1° respectively. While as D2 subset has a total of 320 tampered images in which each copy-move area is scaled according to the ranges of $[0.25, 2]$, $[0.75, 1.25]$ with steps of 0.25, 0.05 respectively. The ability of the copy-move forgery detection algorithm to discriminate between tampered and not tampered images can be done using the subset D3 which includes 50 authentic images of subset D0. CMF Dataset

lacks the substantial modification in the size of the copied region and the integrated scaling-rotation attacks.

- **COVERAGE:** COVERAGE is a multiple-similar but genuine objects (SGOs) dataset consisting of 100 images. The images of this dataset are chosen carefully in order to make the forgery more realistic and challenging. The dataset uses six types of attacks, i.e., translation, scaling, rotation, free transform, illumination and the combination of other stated attacks for forged image generation. However, the dataset gives no information regarding the values of the angle of rotation and scaling, used to create the attacks. Some of the shortcomings of Wen et al. dataset are the limited number of images, the uncertainty of the levels of the frequent attacks used and the lack of post-processing attacks employed for creating the dataset. COVERAGE dataset has distinct ground truth image for the copied region and the pasted region which is unrealistic.

B. Evaluation Metrics

CMFD technique is said to be efficient only when it is able to detect and locate the forgery accurately within the image. The main work of CMFD technique is to categorize the image pixels as authentic or duplicated and is thus considered as a classification problem. Researchers have adopted different evaluation metrics for understanding the performance of their CMFD model. The use of standard and reliable evaluation metrics helps the researchers to compare the results of their forgery detection model with others. The evaluation metrics that are used for evaluating the performance of any forgery detection model and hence classify the image as authentic or forged, are precision (P), recall (R) and F1 score or F-measure and are mathematically defined in Eq. 1, Eq. 2 and Eq. 3. The harmonic average of 'P' and 'R' yields the third evaluation metric called F-measure. F-measure reaches its best value at One and worst at Zero.

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \dots\dots (1)$$

$$R = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \dots\dots(2)$$

$$F - Measure = \frac{2.P.R}{P + R} \dots\dots (3)$$

Where T_P , F_P , and F_N represents the total number of correctly detected forged images; the total number of original images wrongly detected as forged, and the total number of forged images incorrectly missed respectively.

CONCLUSION

Nowadays, forging an image has become an easy task because of the easily available sophisticated software packages such as Skylum Luminar, GIMP etc. Thus, IFD has become an exciting research subject in the field of Digital Image Forensics. In this paper, the classification of different types of image forgery detection techniques is presented, and it is concluded that IFD is multi-dimensional and various characteristics and features can be used for it. It has also been concluded that the Pixel based IFD

techniques are the most effective as compared to the other techniques. Also, after investigating several block-based algorithms used for CMFD, it is observed that the use of frequency-based approaches is more successful in providing precise results with less data processing cost. Additionally, from the study of the different types of CMFD datasets, it is also concluded that there are many features such as image size, intermediate/post-processing operations or the levels of those attacks, size of the copied portion, realistic CMF and number of images that characterize a CMFD dataset. Some datasets are suited for the testing of both Key-point based and Block based forgery detection techniques while others are suited for key-point based algorithms only. Hence, there is still a requirement to develop a reliable and standard dataset for the in-depth evaluation of CMFD algorithms. The performance evaluation metrics viz; precision, recall, and F_1 measure are practical and can be used for the performance evaluation of both the types of copy-move forgery detection algorithms.

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